

Roadmap of soft robotics application in orthotics

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Abstract — New technologies for the improvement of orthoses are being widely studied. This is the case of Soft Robotics, an area of robotics that seeks to create devices with compliant materials that have some resemblance to biological tissues. Due to this, the use of Soft Robotics has shown to be a great option in the orthopedic field, since it is increasingly possible to manufacture accessories that adapt to the human body, providing more comfort and quality of life to its users. This paper aims to promote quantitative bibliometric research for the analysis of the latest studies involving the use of Soft Robotics in orthoses and its scientific development over the years. The results showed that the application of soft robotics is growing, as it has high applicability in different areas.

Keywords — *Soft Robotics, Orthotics, Assistive Technologies, Soft Orthotics.*

I. INTRODUCTION

Soft Robotics is a method that consists in using robotics together with specific materials in order to achieve softer and more adaptable products, in this case, the study applies to the use of Soft Robotics in orthoses. Orthoses are configured as an equipment able to help people with some mechanical or orthopedic restriction, being considered an assistive technology.

The main objective of using Soft Robotics is to obtain orthoses that provide more comfort to their users and solve some problems that exist when using Hard Robotics. This article consists of a bibliographic review capable of analyzing the scientific studies of the last 10 years on Soft Robotics applied to orthosis, in order to collect data regarding the assiduity of publications, types of publications, regions of study, whether the interest is growing or not, and its future perspectives.

II. OBJECTIVES

Analyze the development of scientific work focused on soft robotics applied to orthoses.

III. METHODOLOGY

A. Justification

A roadmap is essential for the analysis of the scientific and technological development of a specific field, since it covers the evolution of the literature over the years. This way,

it is possible to have an overview of how much that topic has been studied, if the interest is growing, and even where there is more research in the field.

Besides the graphic and quantitative perspective, the study of art also collaborates with researchers and industries, due to the possibility of checking the evolution of technology and questioning the possibility of investment in the area in question.

B. Methods

To review the works on soft robotics applied to orthoses, a search was made in three databases: Scopus, Periodicos CAPES, and ScienceDirect. Two sets of words and filters were used to determine that only files containing the terms in the title, abstract and keywords were counted, in order to refine the search. In addition to the filters, the logical operator "AND" was used in all platforms, so that only documents with the two keywords were considered.

As for the publication date, only works from the period 2012 to 2022 were filtered and considered. Since this review is being written in September 2022, the data for 2022 may be updated. Table 1 counts the group of words used.

Keyword group – Scopus, Periodicos Capes and ScienceDirect
“Soft Robotics” AND “Orthosis”
“Soft Robotics” AND “Orthotics”

Table 1 – Keyword Group

IV. RESULTS

A. Database Overview

In the first analysis, the number of documents found in each of the databases was observed. Furthermore, it was possible to see that the Scopus database was the one that provided the largest number of results, and it can be considered a very comprehensive platform.

Number of Works		
Scopus	Periodicos CAPES	ScienceDirect
48	10	5

Table 2 – Number of works included by database

B. Analysis by document type

Observing the types of documents found, it was found that articles were in greater number in all search platforms, indicating that the development of new technologies is growing. Furthermore, conferences paper, books chapter, act of congress, reviews and subscribed journals were also found. Figure 1 shows all the categories and the number of publications.

Figure 1 – Analysis by document type.

C. Analysis by research areas

Addressing the research areas, we can see that in all the databases the application of soft robotics in engineering was predominant. Some other topics were also detected, showing a great diversity of areas that explore the facilities of this technology. Figures 2, 3 and 4 represent the areas found in each of the platforms.

It is important to note that this classification is particular to each of the databases, and cannot be compared to each other, since each one may use different terms for the same thing. We can also see that the same document can fall into more than one category. Still, it is an interesting metric to analyze the multifunctionality that Soft Robotics can have.

Figure 2 – Analysis by research area (Scopus).

Figure 3 – Analysis by research area (Periodicos CAPES).

ScienceDirect

Figure 4 – Analysis by research area (ScienceDirect).

D. Geographical Analysis

Only the Scopus database has available the geographic metrics, and according to them, we identified that the United States is the country with the most studies in the area of soft robotics. Next, some that gained prominence were also the United Kingdom, Brazil and Germany, respectively.

Geographical Analysis

Figure 5 – Geographical Analysis (Scopus).

E. Quantitative Analysis

In this section, we see the metrics of publications by year. When we analyze the data, we see that 2015 had the fewest publications related to the subject. In 2021, it was the peak of documents in all databases.

We can also see once again that in all years, the Scopus search platform was the most complete, obtaining the highest number of publications.

Figure 6 – Quantitative Analysis.

F. Prediction Analysis

In this step, a linear and polynomial regression was performed in order to predict the publication of new documents focused on Soft Robotics applied to orthoses. As a result, it was possible to see that the trend is increasing in both databases. Unfortunately, the ScienceDirect platform has a very small collection, so it was not possible to perform the regression, since a significant amount of data is needed to establish a correct interpretation.

Figure 7 – Prediction Analysis (Scopus).

Figure 8 – Prediction Analysis (Periodicos CAPES).

G. Limb and tissue analysis

In this analysis, we analyzed where the application of orthoses and soft robotics was more recurrent. Thus, we saw that the target of these technologies are mainly the hands/wrists, with 36%, and the feet/ankles, with 31%. This is because these extremities have important roles in performing daily tasks and locomotion of humans, generating great discomfort when their functions are impaired.

Some articles were not computed in this analysis because they dealt with general applications, such as artificial muscles and actuator modeling.

Limb and tissue analysis

Figure 9 – Limb and tissue analysis.

V. CONCLUSION

Soft robotics technologies are essential for the development of more flexible and comfortable orthoses, in order to develop models that are closer and closer to human tissues. According to the data obtained in this roadmap, it is possible to identify that this is still a new method and little used, but it is observed that the trend is that it will be increasingly explored and adapted to existing technologies.

It is important to emphasize that this is a roadmap based on only a portion of the publications related to the theme, since it is not possible to cover all the existing documents. However, this portion was enough to map the development of this resource and make a reliable analysis about it.

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